

Extent of knowledge on falls by staff nurses in Baguio-Benguet healthcare settings

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ABSTRACT

The study aims to determine the extent of knowledge on falls by staff nurses in Baguio-Benguet health care settings. As a descriptive type of research, it necessitates a structured questionnaire as data gathering tool. The researchers surveyed 120 staff nurses as respondents using the nonprobability convenience sampling method and the analysis make use of means and the t-test. Through this study, the researchers were able to formulate a module on falls, its prevention and management in order to enrich the knowledge of the staff nurses regarding falls. In addition, the researchers recommend that there ought to be a manual about fall prevention and management programs in every hospital.

Keywords: *falls, knowledge, Baguio-Benguet hospitals*

I. INTRODUCTION

Vicki Stephens went to a hospital's outpatient department for a hernia assessment. Six hours later she emerged with her face looking like it "had been hit by the rear end of a bus". The 69-year old woman had two black eyes and lacerations after fainting and falling face-first on to the emergency department floor from a wheelchair. She was claiming when she was left unattended by the staff, despite warning them she was feeling light-headed and short of breath. "The hospital bundled me home as quickly as they could with no follow-up plan for my facial injuries. No one has called to check if I am okay. I

feel like the hospital must have a duty of care because they left me unattended."

- Sunshine Coast News, February 1, 2010

The American Nurses Association in its National Database for Nursing Quality Indicators (2009) defined Falls as unplanned descent to the floor or extension of the floor, (e.g. trash can or other equipment) with or without injury.

According to Morse (2009), there are three classifications of falls: accidental, unanticipated physiological, and anticipated physiological. Accidental falls which contribute to 14 % of inpatient falls, are caused by the patient slipping or tripping, usually attributed to environmental hazard such as water on the floor. Unanticipated

physiological falls which make up 8 % of hospital falls, are attributed to physiological factors that cannot be predicted before the first fall. Anticipated physiological are falls by person considered at risk for falling, which comprise about 78 % of hospital falls. Accidental and anticipated physiological falls has long been a subject for researches to prevent up to 92 % of hospital falls and this research is no different wherein the extent of knowledge of staff nurses on accidental and anticipated physiological falls will be determined.

Falls in health care settings are yet a considerable challenge across all age groups, with the older adults being more vulnerable to falls due to physiological changes. Decreasing vision, poor balance, dizziness from low blood pressure and/or medications, and environment factors such as inadequately marked step, broken furniture, loose rugs, and poorly equipped bath areas are the most common causes of falls among older adults (Hogstel, 2005). Fall risk increases as one ages, as indicated by the study conducted by National Center for Inquiry Prevention in 2007.

According to the Center for Disease Control (2006), one of every three older adults falls each year, hence, with the increasing population of older adults, the healthcare workers should be intensively prepared to prevent falls. The United Nations Statistics Division (2000) found out that since 2005, there are fall cases among 672 million older adults and this is projected to increase up to 1.9 billion by 2050.

In the United States, falls are the leading cause of accidents for people over the age of 65 (CDC, 2007). Falls among hospital inpatients are common, generally ranging from 2.3 to 7 falls per 1, 000 patient days (Halfon et al., 2001). Approximately 30 % of inpatient falls result in injury, with four to six percent resulting in serious injury (Ash, Macleod, & Clark, 1998). These fall-related injuries could lead to death, making falls the number one cause of injury- related death for males 80 years old and older and for

females 75 years old and older (National Safety Council, 2009). With the increasing incidence of inpatient hospital falls in the United States, the National Patient Safety Goals, under the Joint Commission on Accreditation of Healthcare Organizations, advocates for institution- wide risk assessment for falls and documentation of a fall-prevention program (VHA National Center for Patient Safety, 2004).

The trend of increasing number of fall-related cases among the elderly population is not different in the Philippines. According to the United Nations Statistics Division (2000), by 2025, the proportion of these incidents is projected to rise to 7.68 million or about eight percent of the total population.

Falls are common, frequently unreported yet preventable, and are often the cause of injury and unnecessary restriction of activity among elderly patients. Falls contribute to the reduction of overall health and quality of life (Rubenstein & Josephson, 2002). In fact, falls are the most common type of hospital accident, reportedly accounting for up to 70 percent of hospital accidents (Krauss et al., 2004). Consequences of falls in hospitals can vary from no effect at all to severe injuries or even death. Between 30 to 40 percent of falls in hospitals cause injuries (Halfon, Egli, Van Melle & Vagnair, 2001), with most common injuries being soft tissue injuries, fractures, and cranial trauma (Chu, et al., 1999). Hence, falls can cause an increasing need for additional diagnostic procedures and increasing stress for the elderly and their families. Even if there is no injury, elderly patients often lose confidence in their mobility, which can cause them to reduce their walking and other activities. Over time, falls can result in deconditioning which increases the risk of further falls (Hendrich, 2003).

The primordial aim of the Nursing Law is primarily to protect the public. Thus, the accountability of nurses to their patients for their nursing services is presumed (Robles & Dionisio, 2001). Nurses can be held legally liable

if proven guilty of malpractice, which may force them to compensation that includes medical expenses, lost salary, a certain sum of money or pain and suffering, and sometimes for emotional damages (Robles & Dionisio, 2001).

According to the Philippine Health Statistics Report from the Department of Health, the mortality rate of accidents including falls was 42.3 per 100, 000 population in 2002. Accurate data are still lacking as to the morbidity and mortality of hospital falls. The newly-established National Electronic Injury Surveillance System is still in its pilot stage, thus, injury data from hospitals are likewise not currently consolidated nationally.

There is no current available statistics of hospital fall incidents among elderly in the region. Precise data to the actual number of fall incidents are uncertain since disclosures are far rarer than errors (Blendon et al., 2001). This may be caused by the typical reaction of healthcare workers best described by an excerpt from an interview with a healthcare worker (Wu, 2000):

“Virtually every practitioner knows the sickening realization of making a bad mistake. You feel singled out and exposed— seized by the instinct to see if anyone has noticed. You agonize about what to do, whether to tell anyone, what to say. Later, the event plays itself over and over in your mind. You question your competence but fear being discovered. You know you should confess, but dread the prospect of potential punishment and of the patient’s anger”.

The Joint Commission on Accreditation of Healthcare Organizations (2006) reviewed patient fall incidents between 1995 and 2004, and found out that the primary root causes of falls as reported by healthcare organizations are: (a) inadequate staff communication; (b) incomplete patient assessment and reassessment; (c) environmental issues; (d) incomplete care

planning and unavailable or delayed care provision; and (e) an incomplete orientation and training. Some or most stated factors stated are present in most of the healthcare organizations in the country. Since four of the five root causes of falls identified by the JCAHO are directly linked to healthcare providers’ capabilities and efforts, nurses’ lack of knowledge and updates on fall prevention may affect the provision of safe and quality nursing care.

Safely, the freedom from psychological and physical injury, is a basic human need (Potter & Perry, 2007). In fact, safety is a need next to the most important physiological needs in Maslow’s Hierarchy of Needs, 2000. Because nursing is concerned with promoting health, which is defined by the World Health Organization (WHO) as the extent to which an individual is able to satisfy needs and the complete physical, mental and social well-being and not merely the absence of disease and infirmity (Bok, 2008). It is one of the inherent functions of nurses to keep the patient away from harm. Nurses’ responsibilities and legal obligations include evaluating each patient’s safety and acting. According to the Philippine Board of Nursing (2009), providing safe and quality nursing care is one of the eleven key areas of responsibility for Filipino nurses. This patient care competency is indicated by performing age- specific safety measures in all aspects of client care (Board of Nursing, 2009).

Falls can produce physical and psychological complications to older adults and such can be the results of poor nursing care. In the United States of America, fall rates in hospitals are included in nursing quality indicators, which are monitored by the American Nurses Association and by the National Quality Forum (ANA, 2009). As a nursing quality indicator, high fall rates imply poor quality nursing services.

Quality and excellence in the care of the patients are the goals of nursing practice. To do these, nurses must see to it that quality nursing care and practice meet the optimum standard

of safe nursing practice (Code of Ethics for Philippine Registered Nurses, 2004). However, in the drive to cut healthcare costs, there has been a steady drumbeat to do more with less, forcing overburdened personnel to the edge of the safety envelope that increased risks exist for patients (Henriksen, 2007). With various issues in the healthcare setting, patient safety is sometimes compromised.

While older adult falls continue to be a problem in hospitals, the research results offer help for clinicians in practice today by igniting awareness to hospital administrators and chief nurses of the importance of staff nurses' knowledge on fall prevention and management. Study results can serve as an assessment on the current knowledge as to fall prevention and post-fall care, making way for quality improvement efforts and staff development programs. These can provide ways for the staff nurses to strengthen their roles in preventing falls and doing post-fall interventions. Moreover, the study results can also be a basis for formulating good nursing care plans. The formulated module hopes to contribute to staff nurses' knowledge on falls, how to prevent them and what to do if they happen, and assist in their provision of quality care.

In nursing education, it is a challenge to produce knowledgeable nurses. The research anticipates contributing information to the existing dearth of knowledge on falls and gives ideas to faculty members on what areas to give emphasis to in teaching student nurses. The results can also aid in curriculum development for the safe and quality nursing practice of future staff nurses.

Theories provide structures to researchers. Nursing theories are distinctive because they are conceptualizations of some aspect of reality, viewed from the perspective of nursing, used to describe, explain, predict, or prescribe nursing care (Meleis, 2007).

Neuman's Systems Model has been described as a grand nursing theory by Walker

and Avant (1995). A grand theory consists of a global conceptual framework that defines broad perspectives for practice and includes diverse ways of viewing phenomena based on those perspectives. As a grand theory, the Neuman Systems Model provides a comprehensive foundation for nursing practice, education, and research (Alligood & Tomey, 2009).

The model discusses adjustment as the process by which an organism maintains its equilibrium, and consequently its health, under varying stressful situations. Stressors are tension-producing stimuli with the potential for causing disequilibrium, such as falls.

Falls are stressors which may disrupt the homeostatic process of the older adults. Hence, they should minimize the fall risk factors and employ fall prevention interventions to prevent falls to meet their safety needs. The nurses' role is to help the older adults to dynamically and continuously adjust fall risk factors and do fall prevention interventions.

Neuman (1995) related prevention levels to nursing in the following manner: (a) Primary prevention occurs when a threat to health exists but no stressor invasion reaction has occurred; (b) Secondary prevention happens when stressor invasion has occurred and action is taken to prevent the state of disequilibrium from progressing to the point at which basic structures become threatened; and (c) Tertiary prevention is aimed at reconstituting a system seriously impacted by stressors to restore the system to equilibrium, optimal wellness, or its stable state (Alligood & Tomey, 2009). The above concept is significant to the study since it aims to determine the extent of staff nurses' knowledge on fall prevention interventions and post-fall interventions. Primary prevention is the most valuable of all levels of prevention. Falls are great threats to health as well as to the lives of the older adult patients, thus, considered as a stressor. Fall prevention interventions which include fall risk assessment, preventive and educative interventions, are primary prevention

against falls.

Secondary prevention involves interventions or treatment initiated after the symptoms from stress have occurred. Both the older adults' internal and external resources would be used toward stabilization of the system to strengthen the lines of resistance, reduce the reactions, and increase resistance factors. After a fall, staff nurses institute secondary prevention—post-fall interventions. Patient-centered tasks aim to stabilize the patient and minimize the complications acquired from the falls. Since the incidents of falls affect the whole system, organizational tasks should also be instituted.

Tertiary prevention focuses on readjustment toward optimal client system stability. A primary goal is to strengthen resistance to stressors by reduction to help prevent recurrence of reaction or regression. This process leads back to primary prevention—strengthening the older adults' resistance to another incidence of falls and reducing the already existing modifiable fall risk factors.

Neuman's model also reflects general systems theory, that is, the nature of living open systems and all the elements are in interaction in a complex organization (Alligood & Tomey, 2009). Falls can be attributed by intrapersonal and extrapersonal factors. Intrapersonal factors are found in older adults themselves that may have contributed to the fall incidents. Thus, patient-centered tasks or the interventions done by staff nurses to older adults to prevent and minimize post-fall complications, are imperative. Patient-centered tasks include post-fall assessments and interventions. On the other hand, extrapersonal factors encompass the organizational policies and hospital environment. Hence, organizational tasks or the interventions done by the hospital organization to ensure prevention and management of falls, are also crucial.

The study intends to determine the extent of knowledge of staff nurses on falls. Specifically, the study aims to answer the following: (1)

what is the extent of knowledge of staff nurses on fall prevention interventions, particularly along (a) assessments, (b) preventive interventions, and (c) educative interventions; (2) is there a significant difference in the extent of knowledge of staff nurses on fall prevention interventions when staff nurses are grouped according to hospital affiliation, length of service, and area of practice; (3) what is the extent of knowledge of staff nurses on post-fall interventions, particularly along (a) patient-centered tasks and (b) organizational tasks; and (4) is there a significant difference in the extent of knowledge of staff nurses on post-fall interventions when staff nurses are grouped according to hospital affiliation (where the staff nurse is currently affiliated with), length of service (the span of employment as a staff nurse in the hospital currently affiliated with and is measured in years), and area of practice (the specific unit or area the staff nurse is assigned to at the time of data gathering). The research outputs are a proposed manual and module on falls, fall prevention interventions and post-fall interventions.

II. METHOD

The study used the quantitative, non-experimental, descriptive design with the purpose to observe, describe, and document aspects of a situation as it naturally occurs (Polit & Beck, 2008).

The study was conducted in the selected health care settings in Baguio City and La Trinidad, Benguet namely: Saint Louis University Hospital of the Sacred Heart, Baguio Medical Center, and Benguet General Hospital. Research population was staff nurses from the above-mentioned hospitals.

Nonprobability convenience sampling was used. Questionnaires were answered by respondents who happened to be in the areas where the questionnaires were floated. These are the areas and wards where the older adults are commonly admitted including general wards—

medical wards, surgical wards, orthopedic wards, palliative wards, ophthalmology wards, ear, nose, and throat wards, and specialty areas— emergency rooms, medical and surgical intensive care units, operating rooms, and coronary care units. Excluded were obstetric and gynecologic wards, delivery rooms, pediatric wards, pediatric intensive care units, pediatric surgery units, nursery, and neonatal intensive care units and the psychiatric unit. Slovin's Formula was used to determine the sample size. The respondents consisted of 120 staff nurses or 75 % of the population (161) of staff nurses in all three hospitals. There are 65 out of 94 or 69 % of staff nurses in Saint Louis University Hospital of the Sacred Heart, 22 out of 25 or 88 % from Baguio Medical Center and 33 out of 42 or 79 % of staff nurses in Benguet General Hospital participated.

Table 1 presents the distribution of the respondents when they are grouped according to hospital affiliation, length of service, and area of practice.

Table 1. Profile of the respondents as to the study's variables (n = 120)

Variables	Frequency	Percentage
Hospital Affiliation		
Public	33	27.5%
Private	87	72.5%
Length of Service		
One year or more	80	66.7%
Less than one year	40	33.3%
Area of Practice		
General wards	68	56.7%
Specialty areas	52	43.3%
Total	120	100%

There are 33 staff nurses (27.5 %) are affiliated with public hospitals while 87 staff nurses (72.5 %) are with private hospitals. As to the length of service, 66.7 % of the respondents or 80 staff nurses have one year or longer service, and 33.3 % or forty staff nurses have less than one year service. With regard to area of practice, 68 of the respondents (56.7 %) are in general wards, whereas 52 of the respondents (43.3 %) are in specialty areas.

The tool used in the study is the structured questionnaire. The researcher constructed the questionnaire items about fall prevention interventions and post-fall interventions based on reading books, journals and internet articles.

The questionnaire underwent content validity, which concerns the degree to which it has an appropriate sample of items for the construct being measured and adequately covers the construct domain (Polit & Beck, 2008). Experts in Nursing practice and education in Baguio City were asked to evaluate the individual items in the questionnaire. The panel of experts comprise: Mr. Joselito Datud, Nurse Supervisor, Baguio General Hospital and Medical Center; Ms. Nancy Dakiwas, Head Nurse, Saint Louis University Hospital of the Sacred Heart; Ms. Rufina Abul, Department Head, College of Nursing, Saint Louis University; Ms. Norenia Dao-ayen and Ms. Carolina Pangwi, Faculty, College of Nursing, Saint Louis University. Suggestions and comments from the panel of experts, the Graduate Program Coordinator, Ms. Elizabeth Bautista, and the researcher's Thesis Adviser, Dr. Jose Reinhard Laoingco, were carried out by the researcher.

A pretest was conducted to test the reliability of the questionnaire. The questionnaires were floated to 15 staff nurses in the obstetric and pediatric wards of the participating hospitals. The pretest respondents were not included as actual respondents. The gathered data were statistically treated with Cronbach's alpha. The questionnaire had a Cronbach's alpha reliability value of 0.83 interpreted as very reliable.

The questionnaire is composed of three parts: first part contains the profile of the respondent, specifically the hospital affiliation, length of service, and area of practice; second part is composed of items regarding fall prevention interventions and consists of three sections with 20 items each: assessment, preventive interventions, and educative interventions; and third part is composed of items regarding post-fall interventions and is consisted of two sections with 20 items each: (a) patient-centered tasks; and (b) organizational tasks. The items in parts two and three are stated in declarative sentences.

The respondents were requested to check the appropriate answer on the "True" or "False" box. Some items are negatively stated but were pre-identified as the correct answers. In each section under fall prevention interventions and post-fall interventions, there are eight false correct answers. In coming up with the scores of the respondents, the correct answer in each item, whether it is a true or a false statement, is counted as one point. For items with subquestions requiring multiple answers (item 1 under assessment and item 3 under patient-centered tasks), one or more checks under the wrong box is considered wrong, hence, no point is given.

The data gathering process started with getting the necessary permission from the

selected hospitals through a letter addressed to the hospital administrator and/or the chief nurse. The research was not subjected to the ethics committee of the hospitals.

The questionnaire was forwarded by letter to the respondents informing them of the purpose and asking their consent and participation. It further assured respondents of anonymity and confidentiality.

The gathered data underwent statistical treatment including mean and t-test. The mean was used to determine the extent of knowledge of staff nurses on falls. In determining if there is a significant difference in the extent of knowledge on falls when staff nurses are grouped according to hospital affiliation, length of service, and area of practice, t- test was utilized.

The Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) software was used to determine the t-value and the p-value. If the p-value is equal or less than the preset level of significance, 0.05, reject the null hypothesis.

The following scale was used in the interpretation of the gathered data, based on the following:

$$\text{Range} = \frac{\text{Highest possible score} - \text{lowest possible score}}{\text{Number of Categories}} = \frac{20 - 0}{4} = 5$$

Range of Scores and Interpretation According to Extent of Knowledge on Fall Prevention Interventions and Post- Fall Interventions

Range of Score	Extent of Knowledge	Interpretation
16.00 – 20.00	Highly Knowledgeable	If 80 – 100 % of the expected correct answers were chosen, the staff nurses would be highly knowledgeable on fall prevention interventions and post-fall interventions.
11.00 – 15.99	Moderately Knowledgeable	If 55 - 79 % of the expected correct answers were chosen, the staff nurses would be moderately knowledgeable on fall prevention interventions and post-fall interventions.
6.00 – 10.99	Slightly Knowledgeable	If 30 – 54 % of the expected correct answers were chosen, the staff nurses would be least knowledgeable on fall prevention interventions and post-fall interventions.
0.00 – 5.99	Not Knowledgeable	If 0 – 29 % of the expected correct answers were chosen, the staff nurses would not be knowledgeable on fall prevention interventions and post-fall interventions.

III. DISCUSSION

Extent of Knowledge of Staff Nurses on Fall Prevention Interventions. The Philippines being a third world country strongly emphasizes on health promotion and prevention of diseases and disabilities, and this encompasses fall prevention. As the saying goes, "An ounce of prevention is better than a pound of cure." This practice is observed in various settings including hospitals. Diagnostic, medical and pharmaceutical costs bonded with complications of falls require staff nurses to have knowledge on interventions to prevent falls.

Table 2 presents the mean scores and interpretation on the extent of knowledge of staff nurses on fall prevention interventions.

Table 2. Extent of knowledge of staff nurses on fall prevention interventions in the areas of assessment, preventive interventions and educative interventions

Area	Mean Score	Interpretation
Assessment	13.85	Moderately knowledgeable
Preventive interventions	13.97	Moderately knowledgeable
Educative interventions	14.18	Moderately knowledgeable
Grand Mean	14.00	Moderately knowledgeable

Table 2 shows that the mean scores of all the areas fall within the range of 11.00 to 15.99, with the grand mean of 14.00. Such ratings have a qualitative interpretation of moderately knowledgeable.

In particular, considering the mean scores, the staff nurses have the highest extent of knowledge of fall prevention interventions in the area of educative interventions with a mean score of 14.18, followed by preventive interventions with 13.97. Assessment has the lowest with a mean score of 13.85. This finding means that staff

nurses are knowledgeable mostly on educative interventions, then preventive interventions and least on assessment of fall risk factors

Fall risk assessment is done for the welfare of the older adults and the ethical and professional responsibilities, including a duty of care to protect patients against harm, especially the fall-vulnerable older persons. Identifying fall risks is an essential part of healthcare for older adults because it is imperative to initiate preventive interventions for people at risk for falls. Older adults' incidents of falls, especially if recurrent, may be a sign of unmet medical needs and should accordingly trigger an in-depth diagnostic process and intervention by healthcare workers. Because prevention of falls and fall-related injuries is an important aspect of safety promotion for older adults, all nurses working with older adults are responsible for assessing and documenting fall risk factors. There are few opportunities as simple and as important as fall risk identification to improve patient outcomes and to increase patient safety (Hendrich, 2003).

The item with the highest percentage of correct answers in the area of assessment, "Assess the patient for risk of falls during admission, every shift, when patient's condition changes, and when patient is transferred to another unit before discharge" is only 96.67 percent, whereas for the areas of preventive and educative interventions, the highest percentages are 99.17 and 100 percent, respectively. Incidents of falls happen more commonly in periods immediately following a transition between different settings (Capezuti, Boltz, Renz, Hoffman, & Norman, 2006). Fall risks also vary over time and can change quickly when there is a sudden change in the older adults' status, hence the necessity to assess the older adults for risk of falls during admission, every shift, when their condition changes, when transferred to another room or unit and before discharge. The latter is for formulation of strategies of fall prevention in their home since 15 % of older people discharged from hospital

have one or more falls in the first month after their return home (Mahoney, Sager, Dunham, & Johnson, 1994).

Concepts on safety were probably instilled and grasped by staff nurses through nursing education and hospital exposure as student nurses. They may have learned how to assess older adults for possible risk factors that may jeopardize their safety. Irawaty (1995) supported this with the statement, "nurses, during their early years in school, were trained how to gather complete and relevant information about their patients."

Furthermore, nurses perhaps are very much familiar with assessment, being the first step of the nursing process that all interventions are based on. Nurses can not formulate a nursing care plan to prevent falls without doing a comprehensive and appropriate fall risk assessment from time-to-time. Staff nurses thoroughly assess and collect complete information about their patient condition in order to come up with a good nursing diagnosis, a practice that eventually leads to quality patient care (Mangaoang, 1998).

"Impaired cognitive function, as evidenced by confusion, disorientation, and short-term memory loss, can predispose a patient to fall" is the second highest with 93.33 % of correct answers, which is lower compared to the areas of preventive and educative interventions with 95 and 96.67 %, respectively. There are a number of different behaviors that contribute to increased fall risk in older adults with cognitive impairment, including agitation, wandering and impulsiveness. Cognitive impairment is a common symptom for older people in hospitals, with up to 40 % of older people admitted to hospitals (O'Connell & Myers, 2002). With such percentage, staff nurses may have had opportunities and may have encountered older adults with cognitive impairments during their current and undergraduate training, thus have knowledge that impaired cognitive function, such as agitation, wandering and impulsiveness, can

predispose an older adult patient to fall.

The negatively stated item, "The shift with the highest number of staff has usually the highest incidence of falls," has the lowest percentage of correct answers, 22.50 %. Staff nurses may have assumed that the shift with the highest number of staff has usually the lowest incidence of falls with the notion that with greater number of nurses, fall preventive interventions are intensified. Recent studies (Sovie & Jawad, 2001; Unruh, 2003) say otherwise. More nurses are assigned in areas where there are patients with greater illness severity, needing more assistance and care, thus, nurses have more tasks to accomplish. Such situations predispose the high risk of falls.

The area of assessment obtained the lowest mean score, 13.85, among the three areas under Fall Prevention Interventions. The finding may be comparable to a similar study in the Middle East which found out that nurses' knowledge on the causes of patient falls was low (Mostafa, 2009). This is an alarming finding since lack of knowledge on the fall risk factors would not allow for prevention interventions. Non-intervention against the risk factors could in turn contribute to the incidence of falls. Hence, the lack of knowledge or awareness on fall risk assessment can possibly hasten fall incidence.

This unexpected finding probably was brought about by practical knowledge overpowering theoretical knowledge of staff nurses. It is possible to acquire the skills of fall risks assessment without acquiring the concepts behind. Such was defined by Polanyi (1997) as "tacit knowledge," the cognitive processes or behaviors that are performed without reference to a conscious effort in the part of staff nurses (Altmann, 2007). Hence, staff nurses may have been subconsciously doing fall risks assessment and yet, are not much aware about the fall risks assessment concepts when answering the research tool.

The lack of protocols or non-use of existing protocols on fall risks assessment in older adults in some hospitals may perhaps be a contributing

factor to the finding. Although the process of assessment of fall risks is probably integrated in nursing practice, the presence of protocols may guide and remind the staff nurses on the concepts of fall risks assessment. Through constant practice of established protocols, the nurse may be enabled to develop a greater sense of salience (Benner, Tanner, & Chesla, 2009).

Brain drain may also be a factor. There has been a noticeable trend of outward migration of nurses. The Philippines is considered as one of the biggest "exporter" of nurses in the world. From 1992 to 2006, Philippines has deployed 115, 871 professional nurses as overseas Filipino workers (Lorenzo, 2008). With the significant years of work experience as a requirement in working abroad, the exported nurses probably tend to be the ones who are well-trained, skilled and experienced. Some have areas of specializations but are enticed to work overseas possibly due to economic factors. The Philippines has been mass producing nursing graduates each and every year not to attend to domestic health demands. In the year 2000, it was estimated that 85 % of the total demand for Filipino nurses are found abroad (Lorenzo, 2008). The immediate end-result of this brain drain phenomenon is a shortage of skilled, experienced and knowledgeable nurses in healthcare settings. Hence, some may not be knowledgeable on safety concepts, such as fall risks assessment. This perhaps contributed to the unexpected finding that the area of fall risks assessment obtained the lowest mean score among the three areas.

Another possible factor is the high nurse-patient ratio in hospital settings, which can reach from 1 nurse to 26 patients in private hospitals and 1 nurse to 100 patients in public hospitals (Tan, 2004). With such ratio, the nursing care time allotted to each patient may be minimal, which is only a maximum of 30 minutes to one hour, according to a study conducted in a Baguio public hospital (Kiblasan, 2006), thus, making it nearly impossible to do a comprehensive assessment on each patient. The nursing care

time for each patient is probably fully consumed in carrying out doctors' orders and therapeutic interventions. Most likely, assessment of fall risk is simultaneously done during nursing rounds. The current trend of high nurse-patient ratio may jeopardize older adult patients' safety. If staff nurses lack the knowledge on assessment of fall risk factors and is not done, it is most likely that falls may not be prevented; hence, the possibility of increase in fall rates in hospitals. This finding needs to be given more consideration since a high incidence of falls in a hospital setting is a major concern in any health system.

The possible lack of knowledge or consciousness on fall risks assessment points to the importance of designing a module on falls, fall prevention and management for staff nurses based on the knowledge gaps. The possible nonexistence of a comprehensive fall prevention and management program that encompasses fall risks assessment may also play a role in the staff nurses' lack of knowledge as to fall risks assessment, hence, the relevance of a manual to be proposed to the nursing departments of the participating hospitals. Primary fall prevention continues from assessment to preventive interventions, which are actions to directly prevent falls. Based on the fall risk assessment, preventive interventions are formulated to strengthen the older adults' line of defense against falls. "Maintain consistency in procedures, routines and schedules, and staff, as much as possible" obtained the highest percentage of correct answers with 99.17 %. Older adults are special group of people who requires special kind of care thus, the birth of Gerontology Nursing, a field in the nursing profession that focuses on aging and the aged. With care of older adults integrated in the nursing undergraduate curriculum, nurses early in their education may have been made aware of preventing falls through recognizing and dealing with older adults' difficulty of immediate adaptation to the new environment, routines, procedures and people.

Sudden change can cause confusion or

agitation to older adults, which in turn can lead to falls, hence, maintain consistency in procedures, routines and schedules, and staff, as much as possible.

“Promote early mobility and incorporate measures to increase mobility, such as daily walking, if medically stable and not otherwise contraindicated” is second highest with 95 % of correct answers. Exercise has been shown in different studies to result in a range of health benefits for older people. Activities of daily living not only promote patient independence but can also help to maintain muscle mass, strength and mobility. Physical activity may help improve functional outcomes and potentially reduce fall rates. Media give a great deal of attention to the importance of physical activity and exercises, which may remind the staff nurses of the relevance of simple daily activities that they may have probably learned first in nursing school.

Nursing as a service industry continues to grow and develop new roles. With shortage of nurses, lower budgets and increased number of patients, the trend is to do more with less. The issue of high patient-nurse ratio possibly encourages staff nurses to instigate measures to older adults and their families to practice self-care as much as possible.

“Lock movable equipment after transferring patient” acquired the lowest percentage of correct answers, 18.33 %. Equipment, such as wheelchairs, stretchers and beds can contribute to risks of falls. Ensure that the movable equipment are locked before the older adults are transferred.

The low percentage may be attributed to the common problem of broken, nonfunctional or damaged equipment in the hospital areas. According to the Philippine Daily Inquirer (2009), the Philippine Commission on Audit has found 42.1 M worth of defective and unutilized medical equipment in various hospitals nationwide. In addition, the percentage share of equipment purchase vis-à-vis the total fund utilization among hospitals has been decreasing. DOH

hospitals rely on Foreign Assisted Projects (FAPs) for expenditures on hospital equipment (Lavado, Dunleavy, Jimenez, & Matsuda, 2010). With such problem, staff nurses most likely improvise and sometimes permanently lock the broken movable equipment, thus, decreases the action of locking and unlocking the equipment. As to broken bedrails and foot stools, staff nurses are possibly improvising by using pillows, rolled linens and wooden boxes to meet the safety needs of older adults.

Moreover, the transfers and transports of patients may be frequently done by transport aides, nursing aides and institutional workers. The delegation of work possibly puts staff nurses out of action in the transport and transfer of older adults, making their knowledge with it unreliable.

Preventive interventions ranked second with a mean score of 13.97, interpreted as “moderately knowledgeable.” Preventive interventions are actions to directly prevent falls. The finding may have been brought about by the integrated concepts of comfort rounds and bedside care, both of which are included in the area of fall preventive interventions. According to Collado (1993), provision of comfort is a basic need that a nurse never fails to perform and assistance at bedside is the major core of the nursing profession. Hence, regardless of technological advances and increased technical responsibilities of staff nurses, providing comfort and bedside care is probably never erased from nurses’ to-do-lists.

Hospitals are used basically for treatment (Lavado et al., 2010). Thus, it is most likely that older adults and their family expect a hands-on care. With such expectations, staff nurses probably increase their personal knowledge by immersing themselves in practice (Altmann, 2007).

The staff nurses are only moderately knowledgeable on fall preventive interventions probably because of the possibility of tacit knowledge, wherein some of the staff nurses are probably operating on principles that they could

not articulate (Benner et al., 2009). However, it is worthwhile to emphasize that nursing as an “applied” profession not only requires skills, but also procedural and theoretical knowledge since it is impossible to excel in nursing merely by drawing exclusively from trial and error and from imitation without acquiring and using articulatable scientific knowledge (Benner et al., 2009).

Another possible factor is that one-third of the staff nurses in the hospitals under study has only less than a year length of service. This may have been brought about by the current trend of nurses seeking greener pastures. Western orientation of nursing education makes the graduates marketable to foreign countries; hence, most of the skilled nurses are most likely to work abroad while some who are still in the country are relatively unskilled and inexperienced, and after a year or two of gaining experience, also go overseas (Lorenzo, 2008).

Patient education has long been considered a major part in the repertoire of standard care provided by the nurse (Bastable, 2003). Generally, the purpose of educating the older patients is to increase their knowledge for self-care and management to prevent falls. Patient education can also empower older adults to become actively involved in planning their own safe care. As Coulter and Ellins (2007, p.24) stated, “patient outcomes are much improved when patients are involved in their own care and have adequate explanations and time to discuss their concerns.”

The items “Orient patient to surroundings, facilities, and assigned staff” and “Instruct the patient on activities prior to initiating them” obtained the highest percentages of correct answers, 100 % and 96.67 %, respectively. Orienting newly admitted patients as to the ward or unit setting, the staff and the health care team’s regular checks and procedures have always been a part of the staff nurses’ routine. Providing necessary information about the older adults’ surroundings, the facilities, the assigned staff and the activities prior to initiating them can decrease their anxiety, which in turn can reduce

the possibility of confusion and agitation in older adults and probably lessen the risks of falls.

The nursing curriculum integrates the care of confused and demented older adults. The staff nurses’ basic knowledge may have been honed through training and experience of orienting and re-orienting confused and demented older adults. “Advise family to take their time in attending to patient’s needs” and “Let the family have their way as to the cleanliness and organization of the environment”, both negatively stated items, acquired the lowest percentages of correct answers, 20.83 % and 25 %, respectively. Filipinos are known for their close family ties. The family plays a major role in providing basic care and safety to the older adult. Since the staff nurses cannot devote one 100 % of their time to only one patient, the family serves as the partner in ensuring that the patient will not fall. The culture emphasizes that the family knows what is best for the older adult patient, thus, the staff nurses respect family decisions as to attending to patient’s needs and the cleanliness and organization of the environment.

The area of educative interventions obtained the highest mean score of 14.18, interpreted as “moderately knowledgeable.” Perhaps the integration of health education in professional nursing subjects contributed to the knowledge of staff nurses on educative interventions. Staff nurses during their nursing undergraduate years possibly underwent continuous practice of promoting safety to older adults and family. They were probably taught of the principles in teaching, specifically, what to teach, when to teach, and how to teach older adults. Experiential learning enables the nurses to have a clinical grasp of the situation for them to assess the needs of patients and plan for them (Benner et al., 2009).

Another factor may have been the higher percentage (66.7 %) of respondents with more than a year service. Having more opportunities in experiencing safety promotion through educative interventions, the knowledge of staff nurses with more than a year service on educative interventions may be greater.

Extent of Knowledge of Staff Nurses on Fall Prevention Interventions according to Variables. Significant difference on the staff nurses' knowledge on fall prevention interventions was also measured along variables, such as hospital affiliation, length of service and area of practice.

Tables 3a, 3b and 3c present the extent of knowledge of staff nurses on fall prevention interventions when they are grouped according to hospital affiliation, length of service and area of practice. The tables also contain the summary of the t-test procedures.

Hospital Affiliation. Table 3a displays the mean of the respondents on the extent of knowledge of staff nurses regarding fall prevention interventions when they are grouped according to hospital affiliation. The table shows that staff nurses affiliated with public and private hospitals are moderately knowledgeable on areas of assessment, preventive interventions and educative interventions.

With regard to assessment, the table shows that the p-value is 0.038, which is significant at 0.05 level. The null hypothesis that states "There is no significant difference in the extent of knowledge of staff nurses on fall prevention interventions along the area of assessment

when staff nurses are grouped according to hospital affiliation" is rejected. This implies that the classification of the hospital where the respondents are employed influences their perceived knowledge on fall risk assessment. Staff nurses from both hospital affiliations are moderately knowledgeable, but those affiliated with private hospitals got a statistically significant higher mean score of 14.10 compared to mean score, 13.18, of the staff nurses affiliated with public hospitals.

The significant difference may be attributed by the varied nurse-patient ratio in the two settings. Public hospitals that are designed to cater to more serious diseases, are also accommodating cases that can be handled by lower level facilities such as Rural Health Units (Lavado et al., 2010). Furthermore, public hospitals provide services mostly to the poor. About 40 % of patients in public hospitals are poor, compared to only about 13 % in private hospitals. Such arrangements lead to overcrowding in public hospitals, reaching a ratio of 1 nurse to 100 patients (Tan, 2004), limiting the time allotment of nurse to care for each patient. Staff nurses affiliated with private hospitals have probably more nursing care time to each patient with the maximum ratio of 1 nurse to 26 patients (Tan, 2004). Hence, staff nurses in

Table 3a. Extent of knowledge of staff nurses on fall prevention interventions according to hospital affiliation (n = 120)

Areas	Hospital Affiliation					t	P
	Public n = 33		Private n = 87				
	Mean Score	Interpretation	Mean Score	Interpretation			
Assessment	13.18	Moderately knowledgeable	14.10	Moderately knowledgeable	-2.012	0.038 S	
Preventive interventions	14.06	Moderately knowledgeable	13.93	Moderately knowledgeable	0.285	0.777 NS	
Educative Interventions	14.03	Moderately knowledgeable	14.23	Moderately knowledgeable	-0.350	0.727 NS	

Legend:

S = Significant

NS = Not significant

private hospitals can possibly allot more time for fall risks assessment. For every increase of one hour in total nursing hours per patient day, fall rates were 1.9 % lower (Dunton, Gajewski, Klaus & Pierson, 2007).

Public hospitals are characterized by the minimal fee for services, providing free room and board, and waiving of professional fees for its service patients, while private hospitals, fully dependent on its income, are expected to charge fees (Lavado et al., 2010). With the perception that public hospitals provide inferior service compared to private hospitals (Avestruz, 1995), patients in private hospitals may possibly expect higher quality of nursing services compared to public hospitals in exchange of the fees they are paying. Hence, to put the level up the notch, staff nurses affiliated with private hospitals may be pressured to increase their knowledge on fall prevention, specifically on fall risks assessment.

To equal the quality of private hospitals, some government hospitals are undertaking joint ventures with the private sector, such as one of the participating hospitals in the study. Under this system, charity patients can avail of the same services that pay patients enjoy at a minimal price (Avestruz, 1995).

Another possible contributory factor is the lopsided number of respondents from private compared to public hospitals. 87 respondents (72.5 %) are with private hospitals, while only 33 (27.5 %) represented the public hospitals.

While the Board of Nursing expects each professional nurse to maintain and even develop competencies that are expected of their work. It is their individual responsibility to see that they are updated in knowledge and does not put their patients at risk in the performance of their duties (Board of Nursing, 2010).

In the area of preventive interventions, the table shows that the p-value is 0.777, which is not significant at 0.05 level. The null hypothesis which states that "There is no significant difference in the extent of knowledge of staff nurses on

fall prevention interventions along the area of preventive interventions when staff nurses are grouped according to hospital affiliation" is accepted. This implies that hospital affiliation does not influence the respondents' perceived knowledge on fall preventive interventions. Staff nurses from both hospital affiliations are moderately knowledgeable; however, the staff nurses affiliated with public hospitals got a slightly higher mean score of 14.06 than those affiliated with private hospitals, 13.93.

Staff nurses' knowledge on fall preventive interventions was probably gained through training and experience. High nurse-patient ratio, which is more evident in public hospitals (Tan, 2004), can probably make the nurses knowledgeable in preventing falls in older adults. The increased client acuity levels plus the nursing shortage are most likely putting pressure for the nurses in public hospitals to keep track on the current knowledge of fall prevention to effectively promote safety in older adults. Nurses, even with only the basic knowledge on fall prevention, when exposed to the hospital settings, can probably adapt to how other nurses prevent falls. Through their own experiences in fall prevention, they may have learned effective actions to prevent falls (Benner et al., 2009).

For educative interventions, the table shows that the p-value is 0.727, which is not significant at 0.05 level. The null hypothesis which states that "There is no significant difference in the extent of knowledge of staff nurses on fall prevention interventions along the area of educative interventions when staff nurses are grouped according to hospital affiliation" is accepted. This means that the classification of hospital where staff nurses are affiliated does not impact their perceived knowledge on fall educative interventions, but the staff nurses affiliated with private hospitals got a slightly higher mean score, 14.23, than the mean score 14.03 by staff nurses in public hospitals.

Staff nurses from private hospitals are slightly more knowledgeable of educative interventions

maybe because of the need to involve in planning of safe care the older adults and their families, who may be expecting a safer environment and service in return of their payment of hospital bills. In fact, there are more patients who come in private hospitals for health education, 7.3 % compared to only 1.9 % in public hospitals (Lovado et al., 2010). Older adult patients and their families probably want to keep abreast with the health care team with regard to the current health status of the patient and seek information on how to help in promoting health and maintaining safety of the patient. In this manner, they may gain some sense of power and control to the situation.

Length of Service. Table 3b exhibits the mean scores of the respondents on the extent of knowledge of staff nurses regarding fall prevention interventions when they are grouped according to length of service. The table shows that nurses, both those with less than a year and those with a year or more duration of service are moderately knowledgeable on areas of assessment, preventive interventions and educative interventions.

In the area of assessment, the table shows

that the p-value is 0.091 which is not significant at 0.05 level. The null hypothesis that states "There is no significant difference in the extent of knowledge of staff nurses regarding fall prevention interventions along the area of assessment when staff nurses are grouped according to length of service" is accepted. This means that length of service is not an influential factor in the respondents' perceived knowledge on fall risk assessment. However, it is noteworthy to state that the group with one year or longer service has a slightly higher mean score of 14.09 compared to the mean score of those with less than a year service, which is 13.38.

With statistically equivalent extent of knowledge, staff nurses from both groups may be providing the same level of fall risks assessment in older adult patients. This may be because regardless of length of service, staff nurses have the same responsibilities when it comes to patient safety. Gregorio's study in 1991 affirmed that length of service is not a determinant on the quality of staff nurses' performance of patient care.

Table 3b. Extent of knowledge of staff nurses on fall prevention interventions according to length of service (n = 120)

Areas	Length of Service					
	One year or longer n = 80		Less than one year n = 40		t	P
	Mean Score	Interpretation	Mean Score	Interpretation		
Assessment	14.09	Moderately knowledgeable	13.38	Moderately knowledgeable	1.705	0.091 NS
Preventive interventions	13.88	Moderately knowledgeable	14.15	Moderately knowledgeable	-0.638	0.524 NS
Educative Interventions	14.22	Moderately knowledgeable	14.08	Moderately knowledgeable	0.278	0.782 NS

Legend:

S = Significant

NS = Not significant

The slight difference in the extent of knowledge can best be explained by the saying, "Experience is the best teacher." With longer years of service, staff nurses have more experiences in assessing older adult patients of fall risk factors. Through observation and experience, they have learned the risk factors that contribute to fall incidents and the strategies to minimize these risk factors. Experience is a requisite for expertise (Benner et al., 2009). According to Dunton et al. (2007), for every increase of a year in average nurse experience, the fall rate is 1 % lower. Lower rates were also noted in areas with higher percentage of nurses who have more than ten years experience in nursing. It is therefore, imperative to retain experienced nurses since they are paramount to provision of high quality and safe care.

For preventive interventions, the table shows that the p-value is 0.524, which is not significant at 0.05 level. The null hypothesis that states "There is no significant difference in the extent of knowledge of staff nurses on fall prevention interventions along the area of preventive interventions when staff nurses are grouped according to length of service" is accepted. This indicates that length of service does not at all influence the staff nurses' perceived knowledge on fall preventive interventions, though it is worth mentioning that the group with less than a year service has a higher mean of 14.15 compared to the mean of 13.88 of those with one year or longer service.

Even if promoting patient safety has long been integrated in nursing practice, it is only in the last decade that falls were given attention to, when the American Nurses Association included falls in 1998 as one of nursing quality indicators (Montalvo, 2007). With such recognition of falls, further researches and bodies of knowledge on fall preventive interventions are developed. Most staff nurses with less than a year service have graduated later than those with longer service; hence, they probably had more accessible and available data on fall preventive interventions

during their nursing undergraduate years.

Experience can contribute to advancement in knowledge and skills, however, experience is more than the passage of time or longevity. It is the refinement of preconceived notions through encounters with many actual practical situations that add nuances or shades differences of theory (Altmann, 2007). Benner et al. (2009) emphasized that practice would probably be of little avail were it not preceded by training concerning the relevant features in various situations and some theoretical understanding of appropriate nursing theory. Hence, the argument that despite considerable experience, some nurses may never achieve expertise.

However, the limitation may have been with the clustering wherein there is a thin line between the two groups. The first group have at least a year or 12 months of service and the second group have less than a year, for example, 11 and a half months.

Another limitation is probably the wide categorization of staff nurses with one year and longer years of service, that is, staff nurses with at least a year of service are grouped together with staff nurses who may have significant length of service, for example, ten years service.

Table 3b shows that for educative interventions, the p-value of 0.782 is not significant at 0.05 level. The null hypothesis that states "There is no significant difference in the extent of knowledge of staff nurses on fall prevention interventions along the area of educative interventions when staff nurses are grouped according to length of service" is accepted. This implies that staff nurses' length of service does not impact their perceived knowledge on fall educative interventions, but the group with one year or longer service has a higher mean score of 14.22 compared to the mean score of 14.08 of those with less than a year service.

Being in the same level in the hospital organizational chart, staff nurses, regardless of length of service, are moderately knowledgeable

in educative interventions. Having similar responsibilities as per job description, their routines and activities in safety education may have been also parallel. Yet, with more opportunities in educating older adults on fall prevention, those with longer years of service have slightly higher extent of knowledge, hence, the saying, "Practice makes perfect." Study results show that fewer falls occur with more experienced nurses (Blegen, Vaughn, & Goode, 2001). Retaining experienced nurses and providing coaching from experts are worthwhile investments in promoting safe and quality nursing practice.

Area of Practice. Table 3c displays the mean scores on the extent of knowledge of staff nurses on fall prevention interventions when they are grouped according to area of practice. The table shows that staff nurses, regardless of area of practice, are moderately knowledgeable on areas

of assessment, preventive interventions and educative interventions.

As the table shows, in all areas of fall prevention interventions, staff nurses who are assigned in specialty areas got slightly higher means compared to those who work in general wards. In the area of assessment, the table displays that the p-value is 0.814, which is not significant at 0.05 level. With regard to preventive interventions, the p-value of 0.166 is not significant at 0.05 level. For educative interventions, the p-value which is 0.264 is also not significant at 0.05 level. The null hypothesis which states that "There is no significant difference in the extent of knowledge of staff nurses regarding fall prevention interventions when staff nurses are grouped according to area of practice" is accepted.

Table 3c. Extent of knowledge of staff nurses on fall prevention interventions according to area of practice (n = 120)

Areas	Area of Practice					
	General Ward n = 68		Specialty Area n = 52		t	P
	Mean Score	Interpretation	Mean Score	Interpretation		
Assessment	13.81	Moderately knowledgeable	13.90	Moderately knowledgeable	-0.236	0.814 NS
Preventive interventions	13.72	Moderately knowledgeable	14.29	Moderately knowledgeable	-1.395	0.166 NS
Educative Interventions	13.93	Moderately knowledgeable	14.50	Moderately knowledgeable	-1.123	0.264 NS

Legend:

̄S = Significant

NS = Not significant

Staff nurses, especially the newly-hired, are possibly floated on every ward and unit of the hospital to have adequate orientation on the practices of the areas. As general practitioners, the knowledge on falls and fall prevention may be a requisite as a basis for fall risk assessment and fall prevention interventions implemented on vast number of patients with different diagnoses.

Patients in the intensive care units and other specialty areas have, most likely, more acute and severe conditions requiring more than the regular care staff nurses provide in the ward areas. According to Blegen and Vaughn (1998), the proportion of care given by nurses was highest in specialty areas, such as intensive care units than other types of areas. Due to the need for constant observation, assessment, and interventions, lower nurse-patient ratio is observed in specialty areas compared to general ward. These factors brought about norms and values that staff nurses employ based on specific areas of the hospital. Regular assessment of the older adults' vital signs, comfort rounds, toileting and close collaboration with interdisciplinary members for patient care are some of the norms and values in the specialty areas.

Ward culture may be formed through norms and values of a specific hospital area. Positive ward safety culture, or safety norms and values that result to positive outcomes, can perhaps enable the staff nurses to adapt to become safety-conscious in that specific ward, regardless where they were floated from. Safety culture is defined by Cooper (2000, p.177) as, "part of the overall culture of the organization that affects member's attitudes and perceptions related to hazards and risk control."

A study entitled "Safety Culture Perceived by Health Care Staff" by Andersen (2002) revealed that responses of nurses across the different wards appear to show differences in several of the safety culture indices: communication, stress management, morale and motivation, and recognition of human error. The above- mentioned

results reflected the differences in tasks and work conditions in the different hospital areas. Such variations in task characteristics may give rise to ward- based cultures in a hospital. With possible safety culture in the specialty area, staff nurses are probably more conscious of the fall prevention interventions.

Staff nurses from specialty wards have a slightly higher extent of knowledge on fall prevention interventions in the areas of assessment, preventive and educative interventions because aside from their experiences of handling more vulnerable patients like older adults, safety culture is more intensified in specialty areas of the hospitals since patients catered to are more prone to falls, brought about by the new and unfamiliar hospital environment and physical and functional conditions and limitations (Victorian Quality Council, 2009). Knowledge on fall prevention interventions may be essential in promoting safety to ill-stricken older adults, who are susceptible to falls.

Extent of Knowledge of Staff Nurses on Post- Fall Interventions. After an older adult patient has fallen, there may still be an opportunity to reduce the level of harm by prompt detection and effective treatment of unapparent and obvious injuries, consideration of why the patient fell and application of interventions that could limit the risk of another incident of falls.

Table 4 presents the mean scores of the extent of knowledge of staff nurses on post-fall interventions. The table shows that staff nurses are moderately knowledgeable in areas of patient-centered tasks and organizational tasks.

As the table shows, the mean scores of all the areas are within the range of 11.00 to 15.99, with the grand mean of 13.19. Such ratings have a qualitative interpretation of moderately knowledgeable. This signifies that staff nurses are moderately knowledgeable on post-fall interventions in the areas of patient-centered tasks and organizational tasks.

Table 4. Extent of knowledge of staff nurses on post-fall interventions in the areas of patient-centered tasks and organizational tasks

Area	Mean Score	Interpretation
Patient-centered tasks	13.55	Moderately knowledgeable
Organizational tasks	12.82	Moderately knowledgeable
Grand Mean	13.19	Moderately knowledgeable

Specifically, considering the mean scores, staff nurses have the higher extent of knowledge of post-fall interventions in the area of patient-centered tasks with a mean score of 13.55. The area of organizational tasks has the lower mean score of 12.82.

The above findings imply that patients are the most important in the hospital settings since without them to care for, there will be no clients of nurses, thus no nursing. As Armstrong (1995, p.115) emphasized, "patients are human beings who need respect and they are the main reason for the existence of staff nurses." Patients also identify quality care because they are the main recipients of nursing services. As Wise (2006, p.119) stated, "Consumers of nursing care are important because they define quality care." Patient-centered tasks are nursing activities focused on the patient after an incident of fall which include post-fall assessment and post-fall interventions.

Staff nurses obtained higher mean scores in the area of patient-centered tasks since the percentages of correct answers that they got are generally higher in the above-mentioned area compared to the area of organizational tasks. "Assess patient's functional, sensory and psychological status" and "Assess the patient for injuries at the time of the fall including neurological assessment and evaluation for head, neck, spine, and/or extremity injuries"

got the highest percentages with 100 % and 99.17 %, respectively. Effective care to the older adult who fell starts with assessment of the patient's functional, sensory and psychological status, taking note for injuries. Assessment of post-fall injuries is vital for management of immediate effects of falls such as cuts and delayed complications such as traumatic brain injuries.

Post-fall assessment can also give significant information about the causes and contributory factors to the fall, which can be used to help formulate plans of action to reduce future incidents of falls to the patient and others.

The nursing process starts with assessment. The utilization of the nursing process probably contributed to the knowledge of staff nurses on post-fall assessment. Nursing education also gives emphasis to safety for the sake of the patient and the nurse. The older adults have the right to be free from harm during their stay in health care settings. Staff nurses, on the other hand, can lose their license if proven guilty of negligence that resulted to post-fall injuries. Hence, staff nurses are knowledgeable of post-fall assessment for urgent interventions of injuries and prevention of legal measures against them.

However, in the area of patient-centered tasks, there are items that few staff nurses answered correctly. Only 25 % of staff nurses correctly identified the statement "Suggest that the prescribed medications be reviewed by the physician" as "False". In the past, the nursing profession had been stereotyped as hand-maiden of medicine, with lack of autonomy and power. The explanation was said to lie in nursing's predominantly female workforce and because it has absorbed the values of its own activities which assumed a level of passivity and compliance (Naido & Wills, 2009). Through the dramatic advancement of the nursing profession in the recent years, staff nurses are more autonomous and assertive, as evidenced by expanding roles and independent nursing interventions. However, the autonomy of staff nurses may still probably

not fully realized.

Staff nurses scored low on the above mentioned item possibly because in the hospital settings, review of medications is frequently done by medical students, clerks, attending physicians and consultants. Though, staff nurses can review the prescribed medications themselves to determine if the medicines contributed to the incident of falls. A study exploring the origins of physicians' medication errors in England found that physicians, particularly younger ones, rely on both nurses and pharmacists to keep medication errors from reaching patients. One of the specific errors is assuming that nurses would be aware of the medications the patient was receiving (Worth, 2010). With reliance on nurses as safety nets, medication review is imperative in prevention of consequent fall incident.

The low percentage may also be brought about by inadequate knowledge of medication hazards. Albeit the integration of pharmacology in professional nursing subjects in the undergraduate nursing program, staff nurses was the least knowledgeable of medication hazards among the three practitioner groups—nurses, physicians and pharmacists, according to a study of Markowitz, Pearson, Kay and Loewenstein (2001).

The area of post-fall interventions obtained a higher mean score of 13.55, interpreted as "moderately knowledgeable." Nursing is a humanistic profession, focused on the patient as the recipient of nursing interventions. Patient care possibly comprises the bulk of the nursing curriculum, compared to organizational tasks that are tackled in the Nursing Administration and Management. Henriksen (2007) emphasized, that organizational tasks are not something for which many nurses have received any training. Hence, staff nurses are slightly more knowledgeable on patient-centered tasks than organizational tasks.

The area of assessment being lowest in fall prevention and post-fall patient-centered tasks being high mean score may probably imply a

reactive nursing process which is more of cure than prevention. With the current fad of high nurse-patient ratio, staff nurses may possibly be activity-centered and focused on the "here and now" rather than planning of care for fall prevention. The finding may also imply that with less assessment, more incidents of falls may have been probably occurring, hence the more extensive knowledge on fall management than fall prevention.

The organization plays a big role in instilling safety culture. Factors in the organization such as the staff nurses' working environment, salary, recognition may affect job satisfaction or dissatisfaction. If nurses are dissatisfied, they are not motivated to work at their best; hence, their performance is of low quality that may lead to accidents, such as falls. Organizational problems are often concealed causal factors that contribute or even lead to the occurrence of human error made by frontline personnel (Reason, 1997). The majority of contributing causes to major accidents may possibly be attributed to the organizations themselves.

The area of organizational tasks obtained a lower mean score than patient-centered tasks. The item "Develop and/or review protocol for post-fall patient care" obtained the highest percentage of correct answers with only 95.83 %, lower than the highest item under patient-centered tasks with 100 %. At a minimum, an appropriate post-fall patient care protocol includes responding to the patient's immediate needs for care, using a consistent and standard definition of a fall as adopted by the organization, and reporting the falls incident, using the processes and documents defined by the organization (VHA National Center for Patient Safety, 2004).

Well-defined and written protocol for post-fall patient care may not exist in the health care settings, but staff nurses, through theoretical concepts which may have learned in nursing schools, are probably aware that to prevent another incident of falls, organizational tasks include developing or reviewing the protocol

for post-fall care. The post-fall care protocol provides a backbone for guidance on what should happen after a fall, which may include adopted or organizationally formulated checklists and flow charts to steer staff checking for injuries, deciding when to do fall risk assessment again, and acting to limit the possibility of another fall.

The item “Establish a process for assessment of the hospitalized patient on admission for risk of falling” obtained the second highest percentage of correct answers with 91.67 %, which is lower than the percentage (99.17 %) of the second highest in the area of patient-centered tasks. Fall risk screening to all older adult patients may provide an efficient means of determining that older adult patient is at high risk for falls. Although nurses’ clinical judgment of fall risk is considered as one way of determining older adults’ falls risk status, research has shown that this approach has limited accuracy when used in isolation (Myers & Nikoletti, 2003). Hence, a fall risk screening tool can be included in the formulation of a fall risk screening process as a guide for quick fall risk assessment.

Some hospitals in the region may not be currently implementing a fall risk screening to older adults. Still, staff nurses possibly have the knowledge that to limit the recurrence of falls, establishing a process for assessment of the hospitalized patient on admission for risk of falling is crucial. The knowledge may have been gained through access to the internet, which is a vast source of information on fall risk screening process in health care settings.

Source of knowledge may also be from personal anecdotes of staff nurses’ acquaintances and colleagues from other countries as to the process of fall risk screening in their workplaces.

The third highest is “Develop a Falls Incident Report Form or add a falls section to existing incident report form” with 90 percent. Documentation has long been a part of staff nurses’ daily routine for continuity of care to patients, for communication to other members of the health care team and as a basis for quality improvement.

Fall incident reporting provides data to track fall rates, identify patients at risk for falls and injuries and recognize common contributory factors and causes of falls. A fall incident report form or a fall section to existing incident report form can serve as a guide in documenting necessary information about a falls incident.

While health care setting in the region may have not been developed yet, an exclusive form for falls incident reporting, staff nurses perhaps have the knowledge about it. In this information era, staff nurses most likely try to keep track of the trends in other hospital settings here and abroad about fall incident reporting through internet articles and foreign textbooks. They may not be able to fully utilize the knowledge now in their current workplace but in search for greener pastures, staff nurses may apply fall incident reporting overseas.

The item with the lowest percentage is “Ensure incident data are analyzed annually to define the scope, common causes, and common complications arising from falls” with only 20 percent, which is lower than the lowest percentage in the area of patient-centered tasks of 25 percent. To define the scope, common causes, and common complications arising from falls, falls incident data are analyzed regularly, at least quarterly (The Victorian Quality Council, 2009). Findings from periodic reviews of falls data can help in formulating organizational strategies to minimize fall risks and reduce the rate of falls.

The low score of staff nurses on this item may be contributed by absence of such process in their workplaces. With non-existing separate form or section for fall incident reporting, the data on falls are not analyzed exclusively.

There is an existing computer software for management and analysis of hospital adverse outcomes, such as falls, among others. The Hospital Operations and Management Information System (HOMIS) is a computer-based system created to systematically collect, process, store, present and share information in support of hospital functions. Hospital statistical reports are supposed to be

generated through HOMIS by each hospitals and are submitted on a quarterly, semi-annual, and annual basis (Lavado et al., 2010). The computer software may be expensive but a reliable set of data is probably vital before any performance benchmarking can be done.

Although the DOH mandates hospitals to submit reports on hospital activities, no sanctions are imposed for hospitals that do not submit the reports. Furthermore, the last consolidated annual report was prepared in 2004 (Lavado et al., 2010). Quality control procedures, such as falls statistical reports, are probably accomplished merely for compliance purposes rather than for assuring high quality and safe patient care.

Data analysis of adverse outcomes, such as falls, may be accomplished in the hospital levels. However, results were possibly not shared with staff nurses, as a result, the lack of knowledge may be evident. Staff nurses may perhaps also show disinterest in such organizational activities because it has been emphasized in the undergraduate nursing curriculum that nursing is a humanistic profession. Albeit the subject of Nursing Administration and Management, that touches the topic of adverse outcomes data analysis, is integrated in the nursing curriculum, with lack of actual experience, staff nurses are most likely, still blind on that area. As Henriksen (2007) emphasized, after all, it is not something for which many nurses have received any training.

The area of organizational tasks under post-fall interventions obtained a lower mean score of 12.82, interpreted as "moderately knowledgeable." The finding may possibly have been attributed by lack of actual experience in organizational tasks because of probable absence of such procedures in the health care settings where they are affiliated to. In addition, data gathering and analysis are possibly not done since there are no sanctions given to hospitals that do not pass statistical reports to the national level. Even even if data gathering and analysis are done, the results, perhaps, may not have been shared with staff nurses. Theoretical knowledge may have been imparted during the staff nurses'

nursing undergraduate years, thus, the extent of moderate knowledge. However, while practice without theory cannot alone produce fully skilled behavior in complex coping domains such as nursing, theory without practice has even less chance of success (Benner et al., 2009).

Extent of Knowledge of Staff Nurses on Post-Fall Interventions according to Variables. Table 5a, 5b and 5c present the extent of knowledge of staff nurses on post-fall interventions when they are grouped according to hospital affiliation, length of service and area of practice. The tables also contain the summary of the t-test procedures.

Hospital Affiliation. Table 5a exhibits the mean scores of the respondents on the extent of knowledge of staff nurses regarding post-fall interventions when they are grouped according to hospital affiliation. The table shows that staff nurses affiliated with public and private hospitals are moderately knowledgeable on areas of patient-centered tasks and organizational tasks.

As the table shows, staff nurses who are affiliated with public hospitals got slightly higher means than those affiliated with the private hospitals in all areas of post-fall interventions. In patient-centered tasks, the public group has a mean score of 13.73, higher than the private group's mean score of 13.48. With regard to organizational tasks, 12.97 is the mean score of the public group while the private group got a mean score of 12.76.

In patient-centered tasks, the table shows the p-value is 0.659 which is not significant at 0.05 level. The null hypothesis that states "There is no significant difference in the extent of knowledge of staff nurses regarding post-fall interventions along the area of patient-centered tasks when staff nurses are grouped according to hospital affiliation" is accepted. This finding shows that hospital affiliation is not an influential factor in the staff nurses' perceived knowledge on post-fall patient-centered tasks. However, it is noteworthy that staff nurses from public hospitals got a slightly higher mean than private staff nurses.

Table 5a. Extent of knowledge of staff nurses on post-fall interventions according to hospital affiliation (n = 120)

Areas	Hospital Affiliation					
	Public n = 33		Private n = 87		t	P
	Mean Score	Interpretation	Mean Score	Interpretation		
Patient-centered tasks	13.73	Moderately knowledgeable	13.48	Moderately knowledgeable	-0.442	0.659 NS
Organizational tasks	12.97	Moderately knowledgeable	12.76	Moderately knowledgeable	-0.436	0.664 NS

Legend:

S = Significant

NS = Not significant

The slight difference in the extent of knowledge on post-fall care with the public group getting the higher mean may be contributed by higher nurse-patient ratio in public hospitals, wherein the ratio can reach one nurse for 100 patients (Tan, 2004). With overloading of staff, the risk for falls is high. To manage falls and fall-related injuries, they are most likely knowledgeable in what to do if a patient fell. In addition, with the number of patients that staff nurses in public hospitals handle, they may have learned to work effectively and efficiently as much as possible, thus, the knowledge on post-fall patient-centered tasks is imperative, to save time in one patient and to proceed to the next. It is noted that nursing allotted time care per patient is 30 mins to 1 hr maximum (Kiblasan, 2006).

The staff nurses in public hospitals got higher mean scores in post-fall interventions than those in private hospitals. This finding may possibly implicate that staff nurses in public hospitals are more reactive than pre-emptive. Considering the high nurse-patient ratio, the incidence of falls is possibly in public hospitals too. Thus, it is higher extent of knowledge of staff nurses on post-fall interventions than in fall prevention interventions. This concern may have been contributory to the present perception that public hospitals provide inferior service compared to private hospitals (Avestruz, 1995). Hence, people who can afford the

services of private hospitals prefer them even for services that are offered free in the public hospitals (Lavado et al., 2010). This should be given attention to public hospitals cater to the 70 percent of the population who can not afford the fees in private hospitals (Lavado et al., 2010).

This finding may also be reflective of the mismatched allocation of budget in the government sector wherein curative health services are given 71.9 percent of the budget whereas only 13 percent goes to public health services that involve preventive measures (Gualvez, 1999).

Private hospitals, on the other hand, have higher mean score in fall prevention interventions than in post-fall interventions. With the spirit of competition, private hospitals are more customer-oriented; hence, managerial decisions are to attract and maintain customers (Avestruz, 1995). The investment on technological advances may be more evident in private hospitals. However, hospital technologies in the Philippines are generally backlogged compared to developed countries. Technology vintage in private hospitals appears to be within about 5 to 10 years behind what is commonly used in developed countries. Public hospitals, however, appear to have technology in much earlier vintage, with equipment as old as 20 years (Avestruz, 1995). With more budget on spital equipment, environmental risk factors of

falls can perhaps be minimized with the proper use and maintenance of equipment. Thus, it is possible that private hospitals may have lower incidence of falls.

Moreover, reported statistics show that recovery rates tend to be higher in private compared to public hospitals (Avestruz, 1995). Being customer-centered and the prevention of financial losses through legal suits can probably attribute to this. With possibly less adverse outcomes, patients are more satisfied with the services provided by the nurses in private hospitals compared to public hospitals (Avestruz, 1995).

In the area of organizational tasks, the table shows that the p-value is 0.664, which is not significant at 0.05 level. The null hypothesis that states "There is no significant difference in the extent of knowledge of staff nurses on post-fall interventions along the area of organizational tasks when staff nurses are grouped according to hospital affiliation," is accepted. This means that the classification of hospital the staff nurses are affiliated with does not influence their perceived knowledge on organizational tasks but it is worth mentioning that staff nurses affiliated with public hospitals got a higher mean score than those affiliated with private hospitals.

In contrast to public hospitals, the motivation for the establishment of private hospitals appear

to be based on some financial motive, either to promote practice or at least to ensure financial viability in the future years of operation (Avestruz, 1995). To protect the interest, the power and autonomy in some private hospitals may not be fully decentralized to the level of the staff nurses. Organizational tasks are possibly frequently done by hospital executives high up the rank. With such situation, staff nurses on private hospitals are slightly less knowledgeable than public staff nurses on organizational tasks.

Furthermore, private hospitals are not mandated to report to the national level the hospital statistical data (Lavado et al., 2010), hence, it is possible that they have more tendency not to do data gathering and analysis of adverse outcomes, including falls. The nonexistence of data processing may perhaps have contributed to the slightly lower extent of knowledge of staff nurses in private hospitals as to organizational tasks.

Length of Service. Table 5b displays the mean scores of the staff nurses on the extent of knowledge on post-fall interventions when they are grouped according to length of service. The table shows that those with less than and those with more than one year of service are both moderately knowledgeable on the areas of patient-centered tasks and organizational tasks.

Table 5b. Extent of knowledge of staff nurses on post-fall interventions according to length of service (n = 120)

Areas	Length of Service					
	One year or longer n = 80		Less than one year n = 40		t	p
	Mean Score	Interpretation	Mean Score	Interpretation		
Patient-centered tasks	13.70	Moderately knowledgeable	13.25	Moderately knowledgeable	0.862	0.391 NS
Organizational tasks	12.92	Moderately knowledgeable	12.60	Moderately knowledgeable	0.709	0.480 NS

Legend:

S = Significant

NS = Not significant

As the table shows, staff nurses with one year or longer service got higher means than those with less than a year in all areas of post-fall interventions. In patient-centered tasks, the senior staff nurses have a mean score of 13.70, higher than the new staff nurses' mean score of 13.25. In terms of organizational tasks, the one year or longer service group obtained the mean score of 12.92, while the less than one year group got a mean score of 12.60.

In patient-centered tasks, the table shows that the p-value is 0.391 which is not significant at 0.05 level. The null hypothesis that states "There is no significant difference in the extent of knowledge of staff nurses regarding post-fall interventions along the area of patient-centered tasks when staff nurses are grouped according to length of service" is accepted. This means that length of service is not a variable that influences the staff nurses' perceived knowledge on post-fall patient-centered tasks, however, senior staff nurses obtained a slightly higher mean than staff nurses with less than a year service.

The slight difference in the mean may be explained by the learning experiences of senior staff nurses when it comes to post-fall patient care. Experience is necessary in gaining knowledge and expertise. It is the learning of exceptions, shades of meaning and individual contexts that are acquired only through concrete experiences (Benner et al., 2009). In contrast, new staff nurses may probably still be adjusting to the demands of the job focused on efficiently accomplishing the assigned workload. It may also be during the first year of service that new staff nurses possibly realize the reality of the job that is sometimes far more than the ideal they expected. New to the job, staff nurses adopt to the demands of the job whereby disillusionment may quickly overtake them (Lacanaria, 1992).

Another possible contributory factor to this finding is the unbalanced number of respondents. Most of the respondents (80 staff nurses) have more than one year length of service compared to only 40 respondents with

less than one year service. This may have been brought about by the limitation as to the wide categorization of the group with more than one year service.

In the area of organizational tasks, the table shows that the p-value is 0.480 which is not significant at 0.05 level. The null hypothesis that states "There is no significant difference in the extent of knowledge of staff nurses on post-fall interventions along organizational tasks when staff nurses are grouped according to length of service" is accepted. This means that length of service does not at all impact staff nurses' perceived knowledge on post-fall organizational tasks, yet senior staff nurses got a slightly higher mean score than the new staff nurses.

The above finding signifies that at equal level on the organizational hierarchy, staff nurses, regardless of length of service are with the same extent of autonomy, authority and accountability. However, with the longer duration of service of senior staff nurses, they probably tend to exercise more of their autonomy compared to new staff nurses who may be afraid to make mistakes when they practice autonomy. Experienced nurses in hospitals have mastered a kind of knowledge not available from the classroom (Benner et al., 2009). This can be reflected by the slightly higher mean of staff nurses with one year or longer service with regard to extent of knowledge on organizational tasks.

Through experience, it is possible that senior staff nurses have developed intuition, which is defined by Benner et al. (2009, p.17) as, "neither wild guessing nor supernatural inspiration but is the sort of ability, explainable in physiological terms, that we use all the time as we go about our everyday tasks." Having possibly more experience, the real-world elements of organizational tasks are probably considered by senior staff nurses. Thus, those with a year or longer service most likely have fine-tuned to the health care settings of the hospital they are affiliated with. They may

Table 5b. Extent of knowledge of staff nurses on post-fall interventions according to length of service (n = 120)

Areas	Area of Practice					
	General ward n = 68		Specialized area n = 52		t	p
	Mean Score	Interpretation	Mean Score	Interpretation		
Patient-centered tasks	13.34	Moderately knowledgeable	13.83	Moderately knowledgeable	0.985	0.327 NS
Organizational tasks	12.54	Moderately knowledgeable	13.17	Moderately knowledgeable	-1.452	0.149 NS

Legend:

S = Significant

NS = Not significant

have established working relationships with interdisciplinary health care team members. They are probably well-familiarized with the procedures, policies, and their work setting. These perhaps gave them the advantage to have minor difference in the extent of knowledge on organizational tasks.

But yet again, the finding may have been affected by the lopsided number of respondents, with greater number of those with more than a year service and the limitation as to the wide clustering of the group with a year or more service.

Findings, again, point out that it is a wise investment for safe and quality practice to retain experienced nurses by formulating strategies to increase job satisfaction.

Area of Practice. Table 5c presents the mean scores of the respondents on the extent of knowledge on post-fall interventions when they are grouped according to area of practice. The table shows that staff nurses from general wards and specialty areas are moderately knowledgeable on areas of patient-centered tasks and organizational tasks.

As the table shows, staff nurses in special areas got higher mean scores than those

in general wards in all areas of post-fall interventions. In patient-centered tasks, the specialty area staff nurses have a mean score of 13.83, higher than the general ward staff nurses' mean score of 13.34. In terms of organizational tasks, staff nurses from specialty areas got the mean score of 13.17 while the group of general ward staff nurses got a mean score of 12.54.

In patient-centered tasks, the table shows that the p-value is 0.327 which is not significant at 0.05 level. The null hypothesis that states "There is no significant difference in the extent of knowledge of staff nurses on post-fall interventions along the area of patient-centered tasks when staff nurses are grouped according to area of practice" is accepted. This means that the staff nurses' area of practice does not at all influence their perceived knowledge on post-fall patient-centered tasks; however, specialty area staff nurses got a slightly higher mean score than the staff nurses in general wards.

This finding may possibly be explained by the nature of the more intensive nursing tasks and the safety culture in the specialty area where there is a higher patient acuity. Hence, close care is expected from them. Being in the intensive care unit, the expectations are high when it

comes to patient care—may it be prevention of adverse outcomes or their management. To meet these expectations, staff nurses possibly keep reading articles in post-fall patient care and take continuing courses to stay on top of patient care and safety.

On the other hand, staff nurses from general wards may have more patients to care of whom they may have less allotted time for nursing activities. According to Blegen and Vaughn (1998), total nursing care hours per patient day were lower in general wards compared to specialty areas. The proportion of care given by nurses was also lowest in general wards. Thus, the rate of patient falls was highest in general wards. The inadequate staffing may perhaps contribute to dissatisfaction and delays in providing post-fall care, and eventually, the quality of care and safety decreases. In the survey conducted by the American Nurses Association (2001), it was revealed that 56 % of nurses have less time for patient care.

In the area of organizational tasks, the table shows that the p-value is 0.149 which is not significant at 0.05 level. The null hypothesis that states “There is no significant difference in the extent of knowledge of staff nurses on post-fall interventions along the area of organizational tasks when staff nurses are grouped according to area of practice” is accepted. This means that the nurses’ area of practice does not cause a variation in the perception of nurses on post-fall interventions along the area of organizational tasks.

The slight difference in the means may be rationalized by the variations of standard operating procedures of different units, which are mostly dependent on the various activities in the area. Handling older adults with severe illnesses, staff nurses in specialty areas are probably practicing more the role of patient advocates. Specialty area staff nurses frequently and closely work and collaborate with other members of the health care team. With such roles, staff nurses, consciously or

not, are knowledgeable of the concepts of organizational tasks. Fostering collaboration has been emphasized by many as a key strategy for improving patient safety (Goode, Clancy, Kimball, Meyer & Eisenberg, 2002).

Addressing the Learning Needs of Staff Nurse on Falls, Fall Prevention, and Post-Fall Care. The findings of this research show that staff nurses are moderately knowledgeable on fall preventive interventions and post-fall interventions. However, to deliver excellent and safe care to older adults, they would need more extensive knowledge. To help meet the knowledge gaps, the researcher made a module on falls, fall prevention and post-fall care for the staff nurses. A proposed manual on fall prevention and post-fall interventions was also done by the researcher to be forwarded to the participating hospitals through the chief nurses. The module and manual were originally intended for prevention and management of falls in older adults, however, after review of the research outputs, they can also be applied to general adults.

Some hospital organizations may have not yet established a comprehensive fall prevention program or an in-service educational program on falls. The proposed manual offers help in establishing a fall prevention program and provides a basis for formulating an educational program, such as seminars, as to what specific fall topics are needed to be emphasized and who are the target population that would benefit to the program the most.

The module, on the other hand, hopes to relieve the information gaps on fall prevention and post-fall care among staff nurses.

In addition, there is no current published literature that discusses exclusively the topics on falls, fall prevention, and post-fall care in the hospital settings. The researcher intends to process the proposed manual and module to be patented and possibly for sale for wider dissemination of knowledge on falls among older adults.

IV. CONCLUSIONS, FINDINGS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The study aimed to determine the extent of knowledge on falls by staff nurses in Baguio-Benguet health care settings. Specifically, it sought to determine the extent of knowledge of staff nurses on fall prevention interventions in the areas of assessment, preventive and educative interventions; the extent of knowledge of staff nurses on post-fall interventions in areas of patient-centered tasks and organizational tasks; the significant differences in the extent of knowledge of fall prevention interventions and post-fall interventions when respondents are grouped according to hospital affiliation, length of service and area of practice.

Based on the analyses of the gathered data, the salient findings in the study include: staff nurses are moderately knowledgeable on fall prevention interventions in the areas of assessment, preventive and educative interventions.

When the staff nurses were grouped according to hospital affiliation, a significant difference was noted in their extent of knowledge on fall prevention interventions, specifically in the area of assessment. As to the areas of preventive and educative interventions, no significant difference was noted.

When the staff nurses were grouped according to length of service and area of practice, it was found out that there was no significant difference in their extent of knowledge on fall prevention interventions in all the areas— assessment, preventive and educative interventions.

With regard to post-fall interventions, staff nurses are moderately knowledgeable in the areas of patient-centered tasks and organizational tasks. When grouped according to hospital affiliation, length of service and area of practice, there was no noted significant difference in the extent of their knowledge on post-fall interventions in both the areas of patient-centered tasks and organizational tasks.

In conclusion, staff nurses lack knowledge on falls prevention interventions, which are imperative to prevent fall incidents, and or consciousness on post-fall interventions, which are relevant in minimizing complications from falls and in preventing further fall incidents. Hospital affiliation does not at all influence the respondents' perceived knowledge in all the selected areas of post-fall and fall preventions interventions except on assessment. Likewise, length of service and area of practice do not at all affect the staff nurses' perceived knowledge in all the selected areas of fall prevention interventions and post-fall interventions.

A module on falls, fall prevention and management was formulated to meet the knowledge gaps of staff nurses. A manual is also to be proposed to the hospitals which participated, and to help in the absence of comprehensive fall prevention and management programs.

In light of the findings, the researchers recommend that staff nurses should intensify learning about falls, fall prevention, and post-fall care in older adults. Nurse administrators should develop or improve their staff development programs that include orientation programs, in-service programs and continuing education programs which tackle on prevention and management of falls in the older adults.

The hospital organization should consider formulating a comprehensive fall prevention program that includes, but not limited to, fall risk screening and assessment, post-fall care protocol and incident reporting.

The nursing service of the hospitals should strengthen their patient education program on fall prevention and management to empower older adult patients and their families to self-care. This strategy can be a big help for the appropriate allocation of inadequate financial and human resources.

The research hopes to contribute in nursing education, that results of the study will be used as basis to review the existing Bachelor of Science in Nursing curriculum in relation to the concept

of falls. Nurse instructors should emphasize the concept of falls, fall prevention and post-fall care from older adults to student nurses.

With dearth of local and national researches on falls, further studies are highly recommended. A similar type of research should be made in the future, encompassing a broader participation of respondents, with consideration to all types of interventions and varied variables. Studies should be undergone focusing on other classifications of clients, such as pediatric and psychiatric patients. Studies should also be made on the prevalence and incidence of falls in hospital settings to have tangible data that may reflect the graveness of the problem on falls. Since the Cordillera region has such rich culture, studies should also be made to determine the fall risk factors that may be unique in the region. Validity and reliability studies of fall risk assessment tools should also be considered. Researches on the effectiveness of different fall prevention and post-fall interventions are also encouraged.

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REFERENCES

- Alligood, M.R., & Tomey, A.M. (2009). *Nursing theorists and their work* (7th ed.). St. Louis, Missouri: Mosby Year Book Inc.
- Altmann, T.K. (2007). An evaluation of the seminal work of Patricia Benner: Theory or philosophy? *Contemporary Nurse* (electronic version).
- American Nurses Association (2001). Working conditions top the list. *Nursing* 2001, 31(5), 33-34.
- American Nurses Association (2009). Nursing-sensitive quality indicators for acute care Settings and ANA's Safety & Quality Initiative. Retrieved April 20, 2012 from www.ana.org
- Andersen, H.B. (2007). Assessing safety culture. In Carayon, P. (Ed.), *Handbook of Human Factors and Ergonomics in Health Care and Patient Safety*. Mahwah, New Jersey: Lawrence Erlbaum Associates.
- Armstrong, R. (1995). *The nurse and their patients*. St. Louis Missouri: Mosby Year Book Inc.
- Ash, K.L., Macleod, P., & Clark, L.A. (1998). Case Control Study of Falls in Hospital Setting. *Journal of Gerontology Nursing*, 24(1), 7-15.
- Avestruz, F. (1995). *A study of Philippine hospital management administrative system* (electronic version). Discussion paper series no. 95, Philippine Institute for Development Studies.
- Bastable, S. (2003). *Nurse as educator: Principles of teaching and learning for nursing practice* (2nd ed.). London, UK: Jones and Bartlett Publishers International.
- Benner, P., Tanner, C., & Chesla, C. (2009). *Expertise in nursing practice* (2nd ed.). MA: Springer Publishing Company.
- Blegen, M.A., Vaughn, T.E., & Goode, C.J. (2001). Nurse experience and education: Effect on quality of care. *Journal of Nursing Administration*, 31(1), 33-39.
- Blegen, M.A., & Vaughn, T.E. (1998). *A multisite study of nurse staffing and patient occurrences*, (electronic version).
- Blendon, R.J., Schoen, C., Donelan, K., Osborn, R., Des Roches, C.M., Scloles, K., Davis, K., Binns, K., & Zapert, K. (2001). Physicians' view of quality of care: A five-country comparison. *Health Affairs*, 20(3), 233-243.
- Board of Nursing. (2009). National core competency standards for Filipino nurses. Retrieved April 2, 2010 from <http://bonphilippines.org/index.php>
- Bok, S. (2008). Rethinking the WHO Definition of Health. *International Encyclopedia of Public Health*, 1(6), 590-597.
- Capezuti, E., Boltz, M., Renz, S., Hoffman, D., & Norman, R.G. (2006). Nursing home involuntary relocation: Clinical outcomes and perceptions of residents and families. *Journal of the American Medical Directors Association*, 7(8), 486-492.
- Center for Disease Control and Prevention (2006). *WISQARS Leading Causes of Nonfatal Injury Reports*, 2006. Retrieved May 14, 2009 from www.cdc.gov
- Center for Disease Control (2007). Quickstats: Annual rate of nonfatal, medically attended fall injury episodes, 2007. Retrieved March 29, 2010 from <http://www.cdc.gov/mmwr/preview/mmwrhtml/mm5831a6.htm>
- Clare, B. (2010). Sent home after hospital fall. *Sunshine Coast News*. February 1, 2010. Retrieved February 10, 2010 from <http://www.sunshinecoastdaily.com.au/story/2010/02/01/woman-was-bundled-home-after-fall-in-emergency-roo/>
- Collado, E.P. (1993). *Quality of nursing care as perceived by patients and their watchers in selected surgical wards of VLGH-AFP Medical Center*. (Unpublished Master's Thesis, University of the

- Philippines, Quezon City).
- Cooper, M.D. (2000). Towards a model of safety culture. *Safety Science*, 36(1), 177- 192.
- Coulter, A., & Ellins, J. (2007). Effectiveness of strategies for informing, educating, and involving patients. *British Medical Journal*, 335(1), 24-27.
- Chu, L., Pei, C., Chiu, A., Liu, K., Chu, M., & Wong, S. (1999). Risk factors for falls in hospitalized older medical patients. *Journal of Gerontology*, 54(A), M38-43.
- Department of Health. Philippine Health Statistics Report (2002). Retrieved May 14, 2009 from www.doh.gov.ph
- Dizon, N. (2009). P42.1M hospital equipment “defective, unused”— COA. *Philippine Daily Inquirer* (electronic version). Retrieved April 7, 2010 from http://services.inquirer.net/print/print.php?article_id=20091227-244199
- Dunton, N., Gajewski, B., Klaus, S., & Pierson, B. (2007). The relationship of nursing workforce characteristics to patient outcomes. *Online Journal of Issues in Nursing*, 12(3) (electronic version)
- Goode, L.D., Clancy, C.M., Kimball, H.R., Meyer, G., & Eisenberg, J.M. (2002). When is “good enough? The role and responsibility of physicians to improve patient safety. *Academic Medicine*, 77(1), 947- 952.
- Gualvez, B.F. (1999). Inter-LGU cooperation: The key to the issues of a devolved health care system. *Philippine Institute for Development Studies* (electronic version).
- Halfon, P., Eggli, Y., Van Melle, G., & Vagnair, A. (2001). Risk of falls for hospitalized patients: A predictive model based on routinely available data. *Journal of Clinical Epidemiology*, 54(12), 1258- 1266.
- Hendrich, A.L., Bender, P.S., & Nyhuis, A. (2003). Validation of the Hendrich II fall risk model: A large concurrent case/control study of hospitalized patients *Applied Nursing Research*, 16(1), 9-21.
- Henriksen, K. (2007). Human factors and patient safety. In Carayon, P. (Ed.), *Handbook of Human Factors and Ergonomics in Health Care and Patient Safety*. Mahwah, New Jersey: Lawrence Erlbaum Associates.
- Hogstel, M. (2005). *Gerontology, nursing care of the older adult*. Singapore: Thomson Learning Asia.
- Irawaty, D. (1995). Therapeutic relationship values of Indonerian nurse caring cancer patients, *UPCN Research Bulletin 1988-1995*, Manila.
- Joint Commission on Accreditation of Health Organizations (2006). *Root causes of patient falls*. Retrieved November 28, 2009 from <http://www.jointcommission.org/NR/rdonlyres/FA5A080F-C259-47CC-AA8B-BAC3F5C/>
- Kiblasan, J.A. II (2006). *A research and recommendations for nursing department staffing system of Baguio General Hospital and Medical Center in Baguio City, Philippines*. (Master’s Thesis).
- Krauss, M.J., Evanoff, B., Hitcho, E., Ngugi, E.K., Dunagan, W.C., Fischer, I., Birge, S., Johnson, S., Constantinou, E., & Fraser, V.J. (2005). A case-control study of patient, medication, and care-related risk factors for inpatient falls. *Journal of General Internal Medicine*, 20(1), 116-122.
- Lavado, R.F., Dunleavy, A.B.R., Jimenez, J., & Matsuda, Y. (2010). *How are government hospitals performing?* (electronic version). Philippine Institute for Development Studies.
- Lorenzo, F.M.E. (2008). *Special report: Nursing shortage*. Retrieved April 7, 2010 from http://www.manilatimes.net/national/2008/dec/07/yehey/top_stories/20081207top1.html
- Mahoney, J., Sager, M., Dunham, N., & Johnson, J. (1994). Risk of falls after hospital discharge. *Journal of the American Geriatrics Society*, 42(1), 269-274.
- Mangaoang, J.J. (1998). *Perceived performance of staff nurses of the Bachelor of Science in Nursing curriculum in patient care* (Unpublished Master’s Thesis, Saint Louis University).
- Markowitz, J.S., Pearson, G., Kay, B.G., & Loewestein, R. (2001). Nurses, Physicians, and Pharmacists: Their Knowledge of Hazards of Medications. *Nursing Research*, 30(6), 366-370.
- Meleis, A.I. (2007). *Theoretical nursing: Development and progress* (4th ed.). Philadelphia: JB Lippincott.
- Montalvo, I. (2007). The National Database of Nursing Quality Indicators. *Online Journal of Issues in Nursing*, 12(3). (electronic version)
- Morse, J.M. (2009). *Preventing patient falls* (2nd ed.). NY: Springer Publishing Company.
- Mostafa, G.M.A. (2009). Enhancing nurses’ knowledge and awareness about risk management: System design. *Eastern Mediterranean Health Journal*, 15(5), 1135-1144.
- Myers, H., & Nikoletti, S. (2003). Fall risk assessment: A prospective investigation of nurses’ clinical judgment and risk assessment tools in predicting patient falls. *International Journal of Nursing Practice*. 9(3), 158-165.
- Naidoo, J., & Wills J. (2009). *Foundations for health promotion* (3rd ed.). Bailliere Tindall: Elsevier.
- National Center for Injury Prevention and Control (2007). *10 Leading Causes of Nonfatal Injury, United States*. Retrieved March 29, 2010 from http://www.cdc.gov/ncipc/wisqars/nonfatal/quickpicks_2007/allinj.htm
- National Safety Council (2009). *Slips, trips and falls*. Retrieved November 28, 2009 from www.nsc.org
- O’ Connell, B., & Myers, H. (2002). The sensitivity and specificity of the Morse Fall Scale in an acute care setting. *Journal of Clinical Nursing*, 11(1), 134-136.
- Polit, P.F., & Beck, C.T. (2008). *Nursing research principles*

- and methods (8th ed.). Philadelphia: Lippincott, Williams & Wilkins.
- Potter, P., & Perry, A. (2007). *Basic nursing care of the older adult: Essentials for practice* (6th ed.). Bailliere Tindall: Elsevier.
- Promulgation of the Code of Ethics for Registered Nurses (2009). Retrieved December 10, 2009 from www.prc-bn.gov.ph
- Reason, J. (1997). *Managing the risk of organizational accidents*. Aldershot, UK: Ashgate.
- Robles, A.B., & Dionisio, G.S. (2001). *Philippine nursing law, jurisprudence and ethics* (13th ed). Malabon, Phils.: Giuani Prints House.
- Rubenstein, L.Z., & Josephson, K.R. (2002). The epidemiology of falls and syncope. *Clinics in Geriatric Medicine*, 18(1), 141-158.
- Sovie, M.D., & Jawad, A.F. (2001). Hospital restructuring and its impact on outcomes: Nursing staff regulations are premature. *Journal of Nursing Administration*, 31(1), 588 – 600.
- Tan, J.Z.G. (2004). The brain drain phenomenon and its implications for health: 10 strategic solutions for action by Filipino leaders. Paper read at the *International Conference of the Medical Workforce* sponsored by the United States Commission for Foreign Medical Graduates, Washington DC, 4-7 October 2004.
- United Nations Statistics Division (2000). *New United Nations demographic yearbook 2000*. Retrieved November 28, 2009 from <http://unstats.un.org/unsd/>
- Unruh, L. (2003). Licensed nurse staffing and adverse events in hospitals. *Medical Care*, 41(1), 142 – 152.
- VHA National Center for Patient Safety (2004). *Falls toolkit*. Retrieved May 14, 2009 from www.visn8.med.va.gov
- Victorian Quality Council (2009). *Minimizing the risk of falls & fall-related injuries*. Retrieved May 14, 2009 from <http://www.health.vic.gov.au/qualitycouncil/pub/improve/falls.htm>
- Wise, Y. (2006). *Leading and managing in nursing* (4th ed.). St. Louis: Mosby Company.
- Worth, T., & Pfeifer, G. (2010). In the news: Nurses as sentinels for safety. *American Journal of Nursing*, 110(3), 19.
- Wu, A.W. (2000). Medical error: The second victim. *British Medical Journal*, 320(1), 726 -727.

